

An Analysis of Cultural Types and Categories in Moroccan ELT Textbooks: Primary School Case

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Abstract: Language is not only a tool of communiqué, but it is a clue to discover the culture. It allows the learner to discover how other people in other cultures believe, think, and live within their societies. Besides, culture and language are two topics linked in every ELT textbook. In Morocco, the English language is considered a foreign language that students' study from the secondary school until they graduate from high school. This study investigates the cultural contents, aspects, and categories of the Moroccan ELT textbook TICKET1. This study was conducted by employing qualitative data, particularly analyzing the cultural contents of TICKET ELT textbooks. It analyses the written and visual texts in ELT textbook «ticket 1» adopted by the ministry of education in Morocco in 2018. The results reveal that source culture is dominant, followed by the target culture, then the international culture in the ELT textbooks. In addition, the cultural standards presented in the textbook show how the cultural patterns help present culture in the Moroccan ELT textbook. In addition,

Keywords: culture reference, ELT textbooks, language, culture, big culture, a little culture.

I. INTRODUCTION

British colonialism played a significant role in spreading English culture and language over the world. More than 1.5 billion people learn English in different countries, 750 million are foreign language learners, and 375 million are second language learners (TRT WORLD. com, 2021). Language and culture are two essential components to master a foreign language. As Kramsch (1998) says, "Language is a system of signs that are seen as having itself as a cultural value" (p. 3- 5). Both second and foreign language students obtain culture when they study the language. Alptekin (2002) states, "learning a new language is a kind of enculturation, where one acquires new cultural frames of reference and a new world view. (p. 58)." According to Wenying (2002), culture has some common points with language; both express beliefs, traditions, lifestyles, and ideologies. It is hard to teach language out of the culture. Culture is the outcome of the social and historical situations that people act and shape by language.

ELT textbooks consider on of the primary sources of learning English, whether as a first, second, or foreign language in classrooms. ELT textbooks carried language, and language carried culture. The ELT textbooks have some cultural categories and types to transfer culture. For example, the Moroccan textbook "ticket 1" has a corner for culture; it contains information about other cultures and countries in different fields. For instance, "Gateway" is a Moroccan textbook that contains more than one type of culture." It contains texts from source, target, and international cultures. In addition, it has some cultural categories, such as the big culture, which refers to the community and its people, history, education, and politics (Chastain 1988).

Most ELT textbooks have topics according to the big c and Little c categories. "My route" is a Turkish ELT textbook for grade six. It has some units about the big c and little c; units eight and ten are about two major topics in big c: education and politics. Unit 1, two, and seven are about topics in little c such as life, breakfast, and holiday. On the other hand, the little culture is presented as well, and it stands for food, holiday hobby, work, and how to act correctly in daily situations.

Table 1: the cultural contents for My route

Units	Little C	Big C
1	Life	
2	Yummy breakfast	
3		Downtown
4	Weather and emotion	Weather and emotion
5	At the fair	
6	Occupations	
7	Holidays	
8		Bookworms
9		Saving the planet
10		democracy

Picture 1: the cultural corner in the Moroccan textbook «ticket 1»

A. The significance of the study

At the end of the 20th century, American linguists and anthropologists thought language had only one function: to express the individual's reality. From 1990 until this moment, the linguists who believe in the communicative approach think that language's primary goals are communication and connection to the surrounding environment (Richards, 2006). When the communicative approach appeared to the public, the language changed its goals and became the transmission tool to the culture. That is to say, the culture started to take place in language policy, especially in ELT textbooks (Balboniv& Coan2014).

ELT textbooks are the origin place for learners to pick up the language knowledge and culture, whether in private or public schools and institutions. (Hutchinson, 1987) believe that "no teaching-learning situation, it seems, is complete until it has its relevant textbooks (p. 315)." Second language and foreign-language textbooks carried culture explicitly or implicitly. That is to say, there are two main reasons why textbooks transfer culture. The first reason, Native speakers write most of these ELT textbooks. For example, "English for Iraq" is a curriculum written by Iraqi authors and edited by a foreign author. The second reason, the majority of the textbooks have many types of cultures. For instance, "That is it" is a Turkish coursebook with some cultural references. For example, there is a short dialogue between a Turkish boy and an American boy in unit four talking about the weather in New York.

The ELT textbooks hold enormous cultural types; they include the cultural types, weather source, target, or international cultures. In addition, they conclude cultural categories such as the big c and the little c.

A few studies, such as Özil (2006), wrote about cultural content in Turkish ELT textbooks. Ali AbdulridhaObaid (2015) Al-akraaSarab (2007) examines Iraqi ELT textbooks' cultural content. Another necessary research is for Jing Xiao, who

wrote about the cultural categories, and they are essential in translating culture into the ELT textbooks through the language. This study is the first study of its kind, as it is investigated the representations of cultural types and categories in the Moroccan textbooks in high school. This study aims to search about the cultural types and their aspects in these ELT textbooks. The second focus is to analyze the cultural categories in these ELT textbooks.

B. The purpose of this study

This examination is aimed to reach two primary purposes in the field of culture and language and their relationship to the ELT textbooks. The first purpose is to discover the cultural types in Moroccan ELT textbooks in high school. The last goal is to analyze the cultural categories in these ELT textbooks (Ticket 1).

C. Research questions

The following research questions are to be replied to in this analysis:

1. What cultural categories are presented in the Moroccan ELT textbook?
2. What cultural types are presented in the Moroccan ELT textbook in high schools?

D. Definition of the key terms

A Language: refers to "a system of conventional spoken, manual (signed), or written symbols using which human beings, as members of a social group and participants in its culture, express themselves. Language functions include communication, the expression of identity, play, imaginative expression, and emotional release." <https://www.britannica.com/topic/language/additional-info#contributors>

Culture: defined in its broadest sense, is the totality of a society's unique ideas, beliefs, values, and knowledge. It exhibits the ways humans interpret their environments. (Olivier Serrat 2008, p: 4).

Culture references\ types: is when people refer to something that relates to a country's culture. It might be something historic that happened to that country some time ago or something in the news that day. Native speakers use cultural references to bond with each to discuss shared experiences and knowledge (Collins, 2018).

ELT textbooks: ELT textbooks are among the various means to provide L2 learners with pragmatic content represented in speech acts such as to request, refusal, and apology (Vellenga, 2004). <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F2158244015615168>

Big culture: is about the community and its people, politics, economy, history, art, literature, science, geographical features, and education (Chastain 1988).

Little culture: is about the daily routines, food, holidays, lifestyles, customs, values, eating, shopping, greeting people, gestures, stratification, marriage, work, and acting correctly in daily situations (Brooks 1968).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Language, Culture and ELT textbooks

Many studies have been done before about second and foreign languages and cultural representations in ELT textbooks. Language, whether it is a first, second, or foreign language, appears in everyday life, builds a world of meanings, expresses different meanings, and builds a bridge between you and others.

Language is The central axis of ELT Textbooks. In other words, ELT is the derivation instrument used in schools to acquire language enlightenment and cultural awareness. Textbooks become a determining element since they mark the type and extent of cultural knowledge students will likely gain in the classroom. They are wealthy with topics, ideas, opinions, and perspectives; these topics represent the textbooks' core information. ELT textbooks are sources and places for culture and second and foreign language to meet and reach the learners in different countries. According to Sheldon (1988), there are two types of ELT textbooks. , The first type is non-native specialists who write local textbooks, and they present the target culture but with local perspectives. The second type is the international textbooks that introduce the world culture Choudhury (, 2014).

B. Cultural Types and categories

Many academics analyzed the cultural contents of the ELT textbooks with the use of various types of culture. According to

Cortozzi and Jin (1999), there are three types of culture. The first type is local culture, presenting the local perspectives. The second type is target culture, where the target language is used as a first language. The last type is international culture, which refers to all the cultures worldwide except the source and target culture.

According to Brooks (1968), language teaching and learning culture is divided into two main categories. The first category is the big c, which refers to the extensive culture and points to the most visible things such as popular literature and architecture. The second category concerns invisible things like people, language, cultural norms, social interaction, myths, and legends.

C. ELT textbooks in Morocco

English language in Morocco plays a vital role in the life of high school students. The Moroccan students started learning English in their last year in secondary school. The Moroccan teachers have training about the materials they should use while teaching English. First, teachers in Morocco should know the language and target culture. Second, the need to know about the theoretical framework of the standards-based approach (SBA) after they have an overview of the American council on the teaching of foreign languages (ACFL 1996). Teaching English in Morocco is based on five goals: communications, culture, comparisons, connections, and communities. In every Moroccan ELT textbook, you find a corner for these goals in every unit. The pictures below show how the five goals are localized in the Moroccan ELT textbooks.

The five goals for the Moroccan ELT textbooks :

Picture 2,3,4,5,6: The five goals for the Moroccan ELT textbooks

Communities

Comparison

Culture

2. Study the sentences with "used to" in the dialogue and choose the correct option.

We use "used to do" to talk about

1. habits in the past.
2. habits in the present.
3. habits in the future.

3. Complete these sentences about yourself.

a. When I was younger, I used to

b. In primary school, I used to But now I

c. I used to after school.

d. In the evenings, my family and I used to

4. Write three more similar sentences about your life as a child and share them with your partner.

Connections

CULTURE CORNER

WHAT DO THEY SAY ABOUT MOROCCO ?

1. Read these extracts about Morocco from international mass media. Find out three qualities Morocco is famous for.

I invite you to join us for a once in a lifetime trip to the warm, welcoming and hospitable country of Morocco.

Morocco : A land of tolerance where East meets West and South meets North.

Morocco is one of the most moderate Muslim countries and the government is keen to show itself as a progressive state. It is actively promoting a change in conditions of life of all Moroccans especially disadvantaged groups like women, children, the poor, the handicapped....

2. Conduct an Internet search to find out more about the image of Morocco internationally. Share your findings with the class. Here are some websites to use.

http://www.mnrcm.gov.ma/english/e_page.html
<http://www.friendsofmorocco.org/>
<http://www.morocco.com/>

Communications

GOOD HABITS, BAD HABITS !

1. Discuss the following quotation :

*I read, and I forgot
 I saw, and I believed
 I did, and I understood.*
 (Confucius 551 - 479 BC)

What do you learn from the quotation about the best way of learning ?

2. Work in pairs and discuss the answers to these questions.

- a. Do you look over your English notebook ?
- b. Do you revise what you have learnt regularly ?
- c. Do you use a dictionary when you read in English ?
- d. Do you participate in class ?
- e. Do you do your homework while watching TV ?
- f. Do you revise alone or with friends ?
- g. Do you use other sources (Internet, multimedia, TV, books,...) to study English ?

3. Copy the chart in your notebook and fill it.

GOOD HABITS	BAD HABITS
I usually look over my English notebook.	I never look over my English notebook.
.....
.....
.....

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

The study analysis is based on qualitative data. The study depends on a case study of one of the most significant Moroccan ELT textbooks in high school, Ticket 1. The study chooses this textbook because it is obligatory for Moroccan students in-state high schools. This textbook is for the last year of high school grade, and at the end of the year, students will have a final exam in reading, grammar, and writing. When the students succeed in the exam, their English level is upper-intermediate, and they can communicate fluently and express themselves easily. The analysis of two ELT textbooks aims to determine how the cultural types and categories are introduced in Moroccan ELT textbooks.

Table 2: Information about textbooks under the analysis (Ticket 1).

Textbook	Page	Unit numbers	Grade
Ticket 1	162	Ten units	11'

The study also depends on tables that check every unit and determine how the cultural types and categories are presented in the ELT textbook. The data in the tables were collected from ELT textbook Ticket 1, which is a Moroccan ELT textbook (2006) accredited by the Ministry of Education in Morocco.

B. Instrument:

B. 1. Textbooks:

The Moroccan ELT textbook analyzed the first and second research questions about the cultural categories and types. The study examined every unit to determine which cultural class is more or less dominant. The study analyzed written texts to get exact data about the cultural categories and types in ELT textbooks in Moroccan high schools. The data taken from Ticket 1 are noted in the tables below.

The table below contains some little c and big C topics, such as politics, food, education, and economy.

Table 3: The Cultural Categories themes in Ticket 1

BigCthemes	Unit 1		Unit 2		Unit 3		Unit 4		Unit 5		Unit 6		Unit 7		Unit 8		Unit 9		Unit 10		
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	
Politics																					
Social norms																					
Music																					
Economy																					
Literature																					
Education																					
History																					
Geography																					

The table above describes topics under the big C culture category, such as history, social norms, and politics.

Table 4: Describes the most popular topics under the little c category

Little themes	Unit 1		Unit 2		Unit 3		Unit 4		Unit 5		Unit 6		Unit 7		Unit 8		Unit 9		Unit 10		
	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	
Values																					
Lifestyles																					
Customs																					
Hobbies																					
Holiday																					
Food																					

The table above describes the most popular topics under the little c category. There are some famous categories such as food, holiday, and hobbies.

The table is about the cultural types in the Moroccan ELT textbooks. The table divided the cultural categories into three sections. The first one is about source culture, the second section is about the target culture, and the last area is international culture.

Table 5: The Cultural Types topics in Ticket 1

Unit and cultural aspects		Source		Target		International	
		Ticket 1	Ticket 2	Ticket 1	Ticket 2	Ticket 1	Ticket 2
Unit 1/2/3/4/5/6/7 /8/9/10	Names						
	The presence of the women and men						
	Celebrations						
	Food						
	Media						
	Places						
	Art/ literature						
	Sports						

These tables are about the cultural categories and types in the Moroccan ELT textbooks (Ticket 1). The first two tables are about the artistic types (source, target, and international), and the last table is about the cultural categories such as big C and little.

IV. RESULTS

This chapter answers the two research questions about the representations of the cultural types and categories in Moroccan ELT textbooks. The research questions are the following:

1. What are the cultural categories (little and big) presented in Ticket 1 and 2?
2. What types are presented more in Moroccan ELT textbooks? Is it source, target, or international culture.

A. Findings of the ELT Textbook Ticket 1

A. 1. The big culture themes in Ticket 1

The first research question is the cultural categories (little and big) presented in Ticket 1 and 2. the research investigates the two Moroccan ELT textbooks (Ticket 1 and 2) to answer the question. This section belongs to the first part of the first question. The first part of the question represents the little and big culture themes in Ticket 1.

Table 6: The big culture themes in Ticket 1

Big c themes	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3	Unit 4	Unit 5	Unit 6	Unit 7	Unit 8	Unit 9	Unit 10
	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1
Politics										
Social norms		*					*	*		
Music										
Economy				*		*				
Literature					*	*	*	*		
Education	*	*							*	
History										
Geography			*	*						

The table above answers the question about the cultural category, especially the big culture themes. The big cultural themes include (politics, social norms, music, economy, literature, education, history, and geography). In ticket 1, the most popular topic out of all the topics is education, mentioned seven times in all the units. Then economy topic four times. Next,

geography is mentioned four times. After social norms and literature two times. Moreover, music was mentioned one time in all the units, but there is no political theme in all the units.

A. 2. The little culture themes in Ticket 1

Table (6) answers the first part of the second question. This section replies to the representations of the cultural types in Ticket 1. The cultural types include the source culture (Moroccan), the target culture (British and American), and the international culture (other world countries). The results are taken from Ticket 1 and written down in terms of numbers and percentages.

Table 7: The little culture themes in Ticket 1

Little c themes	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3	Unit 4	Unit 5	Unit 6	Unit 7	Unit 8	Unit 9	Unit 10
	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1	T 1
Values										
lifestyles	*	*	*		*					
Customs	*						*	*		
Hobbies									*	
Holiday									*	
Food			*			*			*	

Ticket 1, the lifestyles and customs are the most existing topics; they are presented four times in unit 1/2/3/5/7. Next, the topics about food aspect mentioned three times in units 3/7/10. In addition, hobbies are mentioned two times and holidays one time, but there are no target, international, or source values. The hobbies are mentioned two times in units 1/2. In ticket 2, the values aspect presented more than any aspects. It presents four times in units 1/5/6/7. The lifestyle presents three times in units 1/5/6. The customs and food aspects were mentioned one time in units 10/6. The most minor and last aspect is a holiday which does not exist in all the units.

A. 3. The cultural types in Ticket 1

The table below is about represents the cultural types in ticket 1. It gives data and results about the source, target, and international cultures.

Table 8: The cultural types in Ticket 1

Unit and cultural aspects		Ticket 1					
		source		Target		International	
		NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%
Unit	Names	73	46.49	74	47.14	10	6.36
	The presence of the women	41	60.29	24	35.29	3	4.41
	The presence men	33	41.72	37	46.83	9	11.39
	Celebrations	7	31.81	8	36.36	7	31.81
	Food	3	15.78	8	42.10	8	42.10
	Media	26	40	14	21.53	25	38.46
	Places	38	28.14	23	17.03	74	54.81
	Art/ literature	13	54.16	6	25	5	20.83
	Sports	3	15.78	2	10.52	14	73.68

In the source, the presence of women has the most significant percentage, 60.29 %, then the Art and literature aspects with 54.16. the next aspect is the presence of the source culture names with 46.49%. The presence of men in the source culture is 41.72%, followed by media 40%. The celebration aspect comes after the media aspect 31,81%. The source culture places presented 28,14% and Filling the food and parts aspects have the same percentage 15.78%.

Name names have the most significant percentage in the Target culture types, 47.14%. Next, the presence of men with 46.83%, Followed by the food aspects 42.10%. Moreover, celebrations present 36.36% in the target culture. Then the

presence of women with 35,29% the literature and art aspects present 25% in all units, while the media and places aspects have small, percentages comparing with other aspects; the media presents 21.53% and the places present 17.03%. The last aspect is the sports aspect, representing only 10.52% of all the units.

The last cultural type is the international culture. The most considerable percentage goes the sports aspects with 73.68%.

Followed by the food and places aspects, the aspect of the places presents 54.81% then food aspect presents 42.10% Next aspect is media with 38.46%. In addition, the celebration feature presents 31.81% Art and literature 20.83% from all units.

In international culture, men and women are near each other. That is to say; men present 11.39% and women 4.41%. The last aspect is the names in an international culture which presents 6.36% in all the units.

V. DISCUSSIONS

This chapter aims to discuss the results of the three research questions. The two questions are about the cultural types and categories in Moroccan ELT textbooks and a questionnaire to the teachers to how the presence of cultural types and categories help the students to pick up the language and help the teachers to deliver the language.

A. Discussion of the Findings of the First Question

The first question of the study is "What are the cultural categories (little and big) presented in Ticket 1 and?" The study included two ELT textbooks (Ticket 1 and Ticket 2) from two high school levels; the 11th and 12 grades. The textbooks include the students' books of each level. During analyzing the cultural content in the textbooks, the following cultural aspect was analyzed: names, pictures, the presence of men and women, celebrations and social events, food, sports, media, art, and literature; these cultural aspects were divided into three main types; source cultural aspects (Moroccan), target cultural aspects (American and British) and intercultural aspects (other world cultures). Pictures and texts are the most popular cultural aspects in the two books. The pictures and texts were selected into source culture-related, target culture topics, and intercultural issues. The results show that the majority of the pictures and texts are not linked to a specific culture, and only a few pictures are relevant to the source and target cultures. This result shows that the designers of the curriculums ignored the truth that pictures and texts might present culture in Ticket 1 and 2, and there must be a focus on emerging two cultures (source and target) and international aspects to make harmony. This result agrees with (Loubna 2015) as she explains that when minor importance is given to the source culture, this may let the students away from their own culture.

In addition, names are commonplace cultural aspects in Ticket 1 and 2. That is to say, names are Ahmed, Khalil, and Asmaas Arab and source names, and Jhon and Sara are the target names. The analysis outcome shows that the source names are mentioned more than the target names in Ticket 2, indicating that source culture is more focused on. On the other side, target culture names in Ticket 1 are more than names in the source culture. This focus is relevant as focusing on source and target cultures which keep the students in touch with their culture and other cultures. However, this result agrees with Jafar (2006), who mentioned the importance of releasing a balance between the source and target culture in English textbooks. Celebrations and social events are considered the basis of the cultural aspects; the results indicate few occasions mentioned in the textbooks.

There are source celebrations in the 11 and 12 grades, such as Ramadan and Eid AL-fitr. On the other side, one occasion is mentioned as an intercultural event: Mother's Day. Regarding the 11th grade, there are eight occasions mentioned in the activity book, and it belongs to the target culture. This result may refer to the fact that these books need to pay more attention to the celebration aspect in target and source cultures cultural aspect. Moreover, introducing social activities in harmony might allow the student to integrate more in both cultures.

Furthermore, addressing people is again an important cultural aspect. Results show that the presence of men and women, referring to target and source cultures, is more than the international culture, indicating that the textbooks have a strong connection between the English language and the three different cultures. Moreover, women's results show that they are working in various professions, and it is evident that the function of the target culture speaking community is very different from the role of the source culture society. The presence of women from different cultures, especially source and target cultures in the textbooks, indicates that the textbooks try to show the gap and the differences between women in the two cultures. Results indicate several more cultural aspects found in the textbooks, such as food, sports, literature, and arts. Food is one of the significant aspects that defers one culture from another. The study results show that the target and source cultures do not use enough words and expressions to describe the food aspect, which indicates that the textbooks deal with

aspects of culture fairly and not profoundly. Its culture focuses more on the source culture to give students ideas and enlightenment about their culture. Also, results show that sports, literature, and art refer to the international culture more than the other cultures. That is to say, Sports mentioned in these books refer to international cultures such as India. Art aspect is available in the three cultures especially source and target cultures and writers from both cultures are mentioned. In addition, male occupations and media covered many jobs linked to other cultures.

B. Discussion of the Finding of the Second Question:

The analysis of language skills in all units shows that big "C" culture contained a large percentage compared with the themes in little "c", especially in the listening section. The listening and writing sections analysis revealed that *ticket 1* contained a significant percentage of big "C" culture.

This finding of this study was in agreement with the studies carried out by Xion Jing (2010). The textbook analysis in Xion (2010) has similar conclusions: big "C" has dominated most of the cultural contents. These results show a particular problem with many scholars and experts' ideas in that "little c" culture plays a more significant role in promoting language learners' intercultural communicative competence (Chastain 1988. P,303, Tomalin & Stempleski 1993, Pulverness 1995). They maintain that the priority of culture learning should be given to little "c" in the EFL classroom to equip language learners with intercultural communicative competence" (Xion 2010. P, 90).

Another surprising result discovered from the present study is the top four themes under both big "C" and little "c" cultures from textbooks; social norms, literature, lifestyles, and customs. This was in agreement with Xion's observation presented in Chapter One that said "the textbooks used in English courses relating to cultural knowledge in the EFL classroom in China were still highlight in the introduction of big "C" culture, such as politics, history, geography, literature" (Jing Xion, 2010, p. 90).

VI. CONCLUSION

As Kramsch (1996) mentioned, culture can be presented in textbooks through language. Adopting a cultural approach in the textbooks will set up healthy communication between the sources and aspects of culture. The language teaching materials should introduce a mixture of different cultures and categories. The new improvements in the Moroccan educational system have shown that Morocco aims to ameliorate culture and language teaching materials. Examining the two Moroccan ELT textbooks can flourish as they conscious students of cultural elements and categories. These ELT textbooks and their diversity may allow students to see English as an international language serving the preservation of diverse cultures.

It should be noted that the inclusion of similar elements and aspects from different cultures does not guide increased awareness of cultural diversity and patterns. As (Shin, Eslami, and Chen, 2011) point out, "teaching about culture is much more than a simple presentation of culture facts." however, as an analysis of the cultural depth of the ELT textbooks materials needed to be done, this reminds us of the aim of this study. On the side, this study may support a departure point for developing increased teaching materials. It can contribute to the evolution of "international-mind citizens" by Dooly & Villanueva because they are prepared with intercultural communication competence. Besides, this study's results are anticipated to start an argument for reformed culture teaching in the Moroccan ELT context by raising language teachers' awareness about engaging their students with a multicultural experience and teaching them more dimensions to achieve the standards of teaching English as a foreign language.

REFERENCES

- [1] Al-akraa, Sarab (2013) *Teaching English in Iraq: An Analysis of an EFL Textbook*. (Unpublished Master of Arts in TESOL Thesis). College of Arts and Humanities at the University of Central Florida Orlando, Florida.
- [2] AbdellaAbdalghane, M. (2020). English and Globalization. *Researchgate* : 8-9
- [3] AitBouzid, H. (2016). Boosting 21st-century skills through Moroccan ELT textbooks. *Journal of English language teaching and linguistics*, 1(2), 97-108.
- [4] Alptekin, C. (1993). Target-language culture in EFL materials. *ELT Journal*, 47(2), 136-143.
- [5] American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages. (1996). *Standards for foreign language learning: preparing for the 21st century*. Alexandria: Author.

- [6] AL-Obaidi, Lubna Ali (2015) *The Cultural Aspects in The English Textbook "Iraq Opportunities" for Intermediate Stages*. (Unpublished Master thesis). Department of English Language and Literature. Faculty of Arts and Sciences Middle East University. Turkey.
- [7] Brooks, N. (1968). Teaching culture in the foreign language classroom. *Foreign language annals*: 2004-2017
- [8] Sheldon, L.E. (1988). Evaluating ELT textbooks and materials. *ELT Journal*, 1988 42(4):23/ -246
- [9] Chastain, K.1988. *Developing Second-Language Skills*, the USA: HBJ Publishers.
- [10] H. H. Brown, *Principles and language learning and teaching*, 4th ed. (White Plains, NY: Addison Wesley Longman, 2000).
- [11] Cortazzi, M., &Jin, L. (1999). Cultural mirrors: Materials and methods in the EFL classroom. In E. Hinke (Ed.), *Culture in Second Language Teaching and Learning*: (pp. 196-219). Cambridge: CUP
- [12] Hutchinson, T. and E. Torres. 1994. 'The Textbook as Agent of Change.' *ELT Journal*.48 (4).
- [13] Jafar, F. (2006). The foreign cultural aspects embedded in the English textbooks of the primary stage in Jordan. *Jordan Journal of Educational Sciences*, 2(3), 201-207.
- [14] Kramsch, C. (1998). *Language and culture*: Oxford University Press.
- [15] Merriam- Webster, 1828
- [16] Ministry of National Education. (2007). *English language guidelines for secondary schools: Common core, first year, and second-year baccalaureate*. Rabat: Author.
- [17] Obaid, Ali Abdrida. (2019). A Descriptive Analysis of Cultural Content of "English for Iraq" Textbooks Used in the Intermediate Schools in Iraq. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*: 12-13
- [18] Richard, Jack. (2006). *Communicative language teaching today*. Cambridge University: 21-22
- [19] Xiao, J. (2010). *Cultural contents of an in-use EFL textbook and English significant students' attitudes and perceptions towards culture learning at Jiangxi University of Science and Technology*. (Unpublished Ph.D. thesis),Prince of Songkla University. China
- [20] Yuen, K.M. (2011). The representation of foreign cultures in English textbooks. *ELT Journal*, 65(4), 458-466.